

Study of Magnetic Susceptibility of Dioxouranium(II) Complexes of some Schiff Bases

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Magnetic susceptibilities of dioxouranium(II) complexes with salicylanil and some closely related Schiff base ligands have been measured by the Gouy method. The susceptibility values were also obtained by Pascals additivity method. The two sets of values were compared and the deviation from ideal behaviour has been explained on the basis of Van Vleck's equation. The deviations ($\% \Delta \chi_m$) have also been used to explain the symmetry of the complex molecule. Further attempt has been made to correlate pK values of the complexes with deviation from ideal behaviour. Validity of Ikenmeyer's relation has been tested and found that the relation is obeyed by most of the complexes.

SCHIFF bases derived from the aromatic aldehydes with aromatic amines represent an important series of widely studied ligands¹⁻⁵. Complexes of Schiff bases with various metal ions have been studied^{6,7}. In the present investigation, the authors have undertaken the magnetic study of uranyl complexes of some closely related Schiff base ligands with a view to study the order of ligand field strength, the changes in the symmetry of the component molecules, and to study relation between pK values and magnetic susceptibility of complexes and test the validity of Ikenmeyer's relation.

Dioxouranium(II) complexes of Schiff bases have been isolated and characterised by the authors⁸. The orange-red microcrystalline complexes thus obtained have the formula $[\text{UO}_2(\text{LH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$, where LH is a Schiff base molecule. Magnetic susceptibility study of some of these complexes has been reported⁹. Study of some more similar complexes is undertaken in the present paper.

Experimental

The magnetic measurements were made on a modified form of Gouy balance as described by Prasad and coworkers¹⁰. The apparatus essentially consists of two parts.

Analytical balance: An air-damped single pan semimicro balance of Gouy model and Mettler make with a sensitivity up to 10^{-5} g was used for magnetic measurements. The balance was installed in a closed drought-proof room at a constant temperature ($\sim 28 \pm 1^\circ$).

Electromagnet: The core of the magnet was made up of soft iron. The pole pieces were of truncated shape and nickel plated. The coils of the magnet were wound in eight sections, the windings being of 22 gauge d.c.c. The sections were separated by brass spiders providing ample ventilation.

A low current of 1 A at 460 V minimised the heating of the magnet coils. An ammeter which could read up to 0.05 A and a rheostat to adjust the current accurately, were placed in series with the magnet. With this arrangement a field of about 7000 gauss was obtained in a pole gap of about 1 cm.

The values of specific susceptibility (χ) and molar susceptibility (χ_m) of all the complexes were determined and expressed in (-1×10^{-6}) c.g.s. units. The molar magnetic susceptibilities of complexes were computed using Pascal's additivity law. The values of susceptibilities for uranyl ion and nitrate ion required for this purpose were taken from literature. The experimental values and the computed values thus obtained are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the results that all the complexes studied are diamagnetic in nature indicating that all of them are spin-paired complexes of hexavalent uranium. The computed values are found to be higher than the experimentally observed values as can be seen from Table 1. These deviations are beyond experimental error and therefore are significant.

According to Van Vleck¹¹, the susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule without a resultant spin is given by the equation,

$$\chi_m = \chi_a + \chi_D$$

where, χ_a representing the diamagnetic term is a function of $\sum_n \bar{r}^{-3}$, the radius of all electronic orbits in the molecule, and χ_D representing the second order paramagnetism is independent of

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF URANYL COMPLEXES AND DEVIATION (%) FROM ADDITIVITY

Sl. no.	Complex (Ligand)	Mol. wt.	χ	χ_m (observed)	χ'_m (computed)	$\Delta\chi_m/\chi_p = \chi_m - \chi'_m$	$\Delta\chi_m$ (%)
1.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{ON})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Salicylanil)	788	0.217 8	171.62	210.18	-38.56	-22.46
2.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{ON})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (2'-methyl salicylanil)	816	0.279 5	228.07	234.08	-6.01	-2.63
3.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{ON})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (3'-methyl salicylanil)	816	0.282 1	230.19	235.12	-4.93	-2.14
4.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{ON})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (4'-methyl salicylanil)	816	0.278 1	226.92	234.32	-7.40	-3.26
5.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{ONCl})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (2'-chlorosalicylanil)	857	0.252 0	215.96	239.06	-23.10	-10.69
6.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{ONCl})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (3'-chlorosalicylanil)	857	0.263 1	225.47	238.92	-13.45	-5.96
7.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{ONCl})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (4'-chlorosalicylanil)	857	0.245 2	210.13	238.72	-28.59	-13.60

temperature which arises on account of the mixing of the ground and excited states of electrons in the molecule. If the bonding of the metal with the ligand in the complex is sufficiently strong, the associating units will come very close to the metal

atom, thus decreasing the values of $\sum_n r^{-3}$ and

hence that of the diamagnetic susceptibility of the molecule. This view is supported by the negative deviations observed by the author.

Since the bond between the component molecule is strong, it is likely to bring about a change in the symmetry of the component molecule, and hence affect the χ_p term. Thus, the observed deviations from additivity is the net result of the two opposing effects, χ_a and χ_p which have opposite signs. Since the symmetry of the complex formed may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecules, the change in the χ_p term would obviously be more significant, and hence change in the molar susceptibility of the complex. The greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the contribution of χ_p term to χ_m in the Van Vleck's equation. It is therefore expected that greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the deviation from additivity and vice versa.

Freed and Kasper¹² and Lawrence¹³ have observed that χ_p term is definitely present in uranyl complexes. Van Vleck attributed this paramagnetism to the matrix elements of the magnetic moment operator $\beta(L+2S)$ between the ground state and higher states. The contribution from the spin magnetic moment is zero since all spins are paired-off in the ground state. As the largest orbital contribution comes from the two $5f\sigma$ bonding electrons, Eisenstein and Pryce¹⁴ have assumed that f -electrons are responsible for the magnetism of the uranyl ion. Belford^{15,16} have shown, from the orbital overlap integral calculations, that the $5f\sigma$ uranium orbitals do not overlap much with the oxygen orbitals as the $6d$ -orbitals do and that considerable π -bonding might also be involved.

Since the nature of various ligands complexing with the uranyl ion are similar in structure, it is concluded that comparison of χ_p values will be possible. Examination of results show that the χ_p value vary with the nature of the ligand. Considering the temperature-independent paramagnetism χ_p term as a measure of ligand field strength, the following order of ligand field strength has been established: 3'-methylsalicylanil > 2'-methylsalicylanil > 4'-methylsalicylanil > 3'-chlorosalicylanil > 2'-chlorosalicylanil > 4'-chlorosalicylanil > salicylanil.

An attempt has been made to examine the magnetic susceptibility values of isomeric substituted complexes. A perusal of the values of χ_m suggests that introduction of substituent in salicylanil, in the salicylaldehyde ring as well as in the amine ring at various positions, causes an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility value. Langevin's theory postulates that a decrease in the effective positive charge will result in an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility. An order of increase in the susceptibility values as a result of substitution of different groups at isomeric positions is represented as follows: salicylanil < 4'-methylsalicylanil < 2'-methylsalicylanil < 3'-methylsalicylanil; salicylanil < 4'-chlorosalicylanil < 2'-chlorosalicylanil < 3'-chlorosalicylanil.

According to French¹⁷, if the substituent is *ortho-para* directing, the *ortho* compound should have higher susceptibility than either *meta* or *para* compound, while when the substituent is *meta* directing, the compound has the highest susceptibility values than the other substituents. This difference is attributed to the presence of higher electron density at *ortho* position in compounds containing two electron-repelling groups *ortho* to each other and in *meta* compound to a higher electron density at *meta* position when the two groups are *meta* to each other. The above order indicates that the author's findings are in partial agreement with the above findings.

Since the strength of the bond between nitrogen and the metal depends on the basicity of the ligand

molecule, the dissociation constant value (pK) is a measure of the stability of these complexes. The greater the basicity of the ligand, stronger would be the binding between the metal and the nitrogen, since in such a ligand the lone-pair on the nitrogen atom would be more effectively available for bond formation. It has been pointed out earlier that in the formation of complex salts, the ligand molecule comes very close to metal atom due to strong binding between the metal and the ligand. Due to this strong binding, the compactness of the molecule will increase, thus bringing about a reduction in $\sum_n \bar{\gamma}^2$

value of the molecule, and hence larger deviation from additivity. An attempt has therefore been made to correlate the observed deviations $\Delta\chi_m$ from additivity to the pK values of these complexes (Fig.1), since these deviations also indicate to some extent the strength of binding between the metal and the ligand. The theory demands that the higher magnitude of pK should result in higher values of $\Delta\chi_m$. However, the actual results are not in agreement with the theory and it appears that the electronegativity of nitrogen in the ligand molecule is not the only factor which affects the additivity of molar magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes.

Fig. 1. Graph of ($\% \Delta \chi_m$) of uranyl complexes against pK .

Ikenmeyer's¹⁸ relation was tested by plotting the molar susceptibility values of complexes against total number of electrons in the complex molecule. From the plot, it appeared that most of the points

nearly lie on the straight line (Fig. 2) indicating that Ikenmeyer's relation is obeyed by most of these complexes. When the total number of electrons in the complex is zero, χ_m should also be zero and the straight line should pass through the origin. This

Fig. 2. Ikenmeyer's relation.

observation is in conformity with the one made by Mulay and Prasad¹⁹. It is also seen that all the plotted points do not lie exactly on the straight line which shows that during the formation of the complex the components have undergone deformation, which is responsible for significant deviations from additivity of magnetic susceptibility.

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